

Silver effect on the tribological and antibacterial properties of a-C:Ag coatings

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Abstract

a-C:Ag coatings (1.2-23.4 at.% of Ag) were deposited using magnetron sputtering, Ag nanoparticles appear embedded in the carbon matrix or segregated to the column boundaries or surface. The silver doping has not promoted significant changes of the sp^2/sp^3 ratio although a decrease of the hardness is observed (from 17 to 7 GPa). The tribological behavior did not show a clear dependence on the silver concentration in unlubricated or lubricated conditions (fetal bovinum serum) against alumina or UHMWPE balls. Ag nanoparticle dispersion enhanced the bactericide behavior as determined by the released Ag^+ ion in the fluid media. There is no clear effect of friction rubbing on the released silver indicating that diffusion and top segregation are prevalent mechanisms for its dissolution.

1. Introduction

There has been a lot of interest on amorphous carbon films (a-C) and diamond-like coatings (DLC) in the past twenty years because of interesting chemical and physical properties such as high chemical inertness and diamond-like properties [1,2], low friction coefficient and wear resistance, and corrosion resistance [3-5]. Furthermore, a good biocompatibility has been demonstrated in the last decades by in-vitro growing of different cell types on carbon-based coatings and determining the cell response [6-8]. Due to these properties, the DLC or a-C films are being used in different biological applications [9-14]. Today, two main fields of biological application are being studied: blood contacting implants (such as heart valves and stents) and load bearing joints [8,15,16]. Unfortunately, the use of orthopedic implants is associated with a relatively high incidence of infection. In addition to local pain, infection around surgical implants can cause bone destruction that ultimately, produce loosening of the implant and prevent the bone from healing. The best solution to avoid microbial infections of implants is to inhibit the colonization of the surface by the bacteria. In attempt to address this, advanced antibacterial coating must be developed to prevent infection by decreasing the bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation to the implant, which can also enhance bone growth around the implanted device.

Bacterial adhesion to surfaces is an extremely complicated process that is affected by many factors including environment, bacterial properties and material surface characteristic, such as, chemical composition, bonding structure, surface charge, hydrophobicity and topography-roughness. Wang et al. [17] pointed out that carbon films are energetically unfavorable for bacterial adhesion, and several authors have reported that carbon films exhibit antibacterial properties [18,19].

Surface modification by doping with suitable element such as copper [20] platinum [21], silver [22-25], or combination of them (Ag+Pt [21]; Ag+Si [26]) has been proved to greatly increase their antibacterial properties. Silver has been recognized as antibacterial agents since ancient times, and has been used in biomedical engineering with good effects in many different forms (nanoparticles, nanocomposite, colloids, foams, polymers, fibers, etc.) to hinder the biofilm formation and hence incidence of infections [27]. In this sense, silver-containing a-C films have attracted a lot of attention in prosthesis and implant sectors due to promising antibacterial and tribological

properties [24-34], good hemo-compatibility and hydrophobic characteristics [23,35]. Besides antibacterial properties, silver is effective against a large range of fungi, viruses, has anti-inflammatory properties, and lacks the resistance problems that some antibiotics present [27,36,37]. It has also found application in many consumer products outside of the medical sector, such as textiles or cosmetics [27,38].

When DLC or a-C films containing different amounts of silver are exposed to a biological media, they start to release Ag^+ ions, within days or weeks, causing adverse reactions in the cells attached to the surface [39]. It seems that the toxicity towards bacteria is greater than that towards the human cells being Ag-doped carbon-based films potential candidates for orthopaedic osseointegration [27,40,41]. Furthermore, the application of titanium implants with Ag-doped DLC has inhibiting influence on the growth of some tumours, opening further possibility for its application in medicine [30].

In this work, a series of pure a-C samples was firstly deposited by direct current pulsed (DC-p) magnetron sputtering under different frequency and duty cycle conditions to determine the best experimental parameters in terms of tribological performance. Then, a set of a-C:Ag films with different Ag contents ranging from 1.2 to 23.4 at. % was deposited using a carbon target with silver nuggets on its surface. Although many studies exist on the antibacterial properties of silver nanoparticles and the tribological and mechanical properties of Ag-doped carbon-based coatings, a holistic view considering the mutual influence of the film microstructure, silver concentration and distribution, the matrix characteristics on the tribological and biological properties and their mechanisms of action is still needed. Therefore, in this work an extensive study of the composition, nanostructure, surface, roughness, wettability, bonding structure, mechanical and antimicrobial properties are studied and discussed as the Ag content increases. With the aim of simulating the human body environmental conditions, tribological tests were carried out using fetal bovinum serum as surrounding medium and a constant temperature of 37 °C. The antibacterial activity for *Escherichia coli* (gram-negative) and the evaluation of the Ag released in contact with the medium under tribological solicitation are also presented. The comparative discussion with previous literature data is sought in order to get a comprehensive view of the phenomena involved and mechanisms of action in the real foreseen application.

2. Experimental

The films were deposited by means of magnetron sputtering using a graphite target of 2 inches of diameter (Kurt and Lesker, purity 99.5%) situated opposite to the samples. Power was supplied by means of a MKS source (RPG50 model) using constant or pulsed DC signals at 300 W. A titanium underlayer was used to increase the adhesion of the carbon film by sputtering of a Ti target (Kurt and Lesker, purity 99.5%) located at 90° of the sampleholder. Silver was incorporated in the film composition by including different number of pellets (2, 3 or 4) made with Ag wire of 0.1 mm of thickness in the sputtering racetrack. The Ag pellets were roughly ball-shaped of 3-4 mm of diameter. The substrates were monocrystalline silicon (100) cut in rectangular 20×15 mm pieces placed in a static sample holder. No rotation was possible during deposition and consequently variable chemical composition was obtained depending on the location in the sample holder. The sputtering atmosphere was argon at 5.6×10^{-3} mbar and typical deposition times were 2-3 h.

A series of pure a-C samples was firstly deposited by pulsed DC magnetron sputtering under different frequency (125 and 250 kHz) and duty cycle values (70 and 90%) to determine the synthesis parameters that produced the best tribological performance in unlubricated conditions. A film was also deposited without pulses for comparison purposes. The power applied to the targets was 300W. Then, a set of a-C:Ag coatings with different Ag contents ranging from 1.2 to 23.4 at. % was deposited using the determined optimum conditions and a carbon target with different number of silver nuggets on its surface.

The morphology, thickness and chemical composition of the coatings were investigated by preparing cross-section specimens and subsequent observation by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) performed in a high resolution FEG microscope, HITACHI-4800, equipped with (EDX) (Bruker, XFlash4100), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) in a Philips CM20 microscope operating at 200 kV. Cross-section views were obtained by cleaving silicon substrates, for SEM examination, and mechanical polishing followed by argon ion milling to electron transparency, in the case of TEM observation. For the advanced microstructural characterization a FEI TECNAI G2 F30 S-Twin high resolution transmission electron microscope at 300 kV, with 0.2 nm point resolution was used, equipped with a HAADF detector with 0.16 nm point resolution from

Fischione Instruments, and a X-Max EDX detector from Oxford. The surface roughness was evaluated by means of a stylus mechanical profilometer from Mahr (Marsurf XR20).

Raman spectra measurements ($200\text{-}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were carried out with a LabRAM (Horiba Jobin Yvon) spectrometer equipped with a true confocal microscope, a charge-coupled device detector and a solid-state laser (532 nm) working at 2.5 mW to avoid sample damaging. All the samples were analyzed with 100 s exposure times and aperture openings of 100 μm using a 100 \times magnification.

Nanoindentation experiments were performed with a MTS Nanoindenter II XP using the continuous stiffness measurement (CSM) technique. All tests were carried out at room temperature with a diamond Berkovich (three-sided pyramid) indenter tip. The load–displacement data obtained were analyzed using the method of Oliver and Pharr [42] to determine the hardness and the elastic modulus as a function of the displacement of the indenter. The estimation of both properties was done in the region in which the indentation depth did not exceed 10–15% of the coating thickness disregarding the initial points affected by tip defects and surface roughness.

Tribological tests were performed using a reciprocating ball-on-disk CSM tribometer at 5 N of applied load for 10000 cycles. The track length was 10 mm and the sliding frequency was 2 Hz. Different types of counterface material and surrounding media were employed: 6-mm 100Cr6 balls (with no liquid media) to investigate the tribological properties of the carbon coatings in dry conditions and 6-mm alumina ball in 30 ml of fetal bovinum serum (FBS) at 37 °C to simulate body conditions. In addition, 10-mm ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) balls were employed in FBS at 37 °C to mimic the tribological system in prosthesis. The first set of tribological experiments in unlubricated conditions enabled to identify the synthesis conditions yielding the most self-lubricant coatings. Second, the employment of alumina balls and FBS allowed to determine the wear resistance of the films in conditions close to application. Al_2O_3 is a hard ceramic material that guarantees chemical inertness during the friction test and able to generate measurable film wear. The last step consisted in the analysis of the tribological behavior in conditions similar to those found in implants. Although the deposition was not done on final application substrate (typically titanium-based alloys), silicon was selected for this preliminary

study for practical reasons. Tribological processes refer to surfaces in contact and relative motion and therefore the counterfaces under investigation are not directly influenced by the substrate underneath. Nevertheless, as a titanium underlayer was previously deposited on all silicon pieces the studied coating system approaches the final tribological design.

Hydrophobicity analysis was performed through static water contact angle measurements with OCA20 equipment and SCA20 software (Dataphysics). Bidistilled water sessile drops of 1 μ l were employed. The reported values are an average of ten measurements taken for each examined surface of coatings deposited on silicon.

Two different antimicrobial assays on the coated surfaces were performed as follows. (A) Qualitative assay: A cell suspension of *Escherichia coli* K12 (ca. 10^6 cfu – colony-forming units) was spread onto the surface of a 10 cm-diameter Luria-Bertani agar plate (LB agar lennox; Pronadisa 1083.00) and let dry. Next, 5 mm-side square coated samples, sterilized by UV for 15 min, were placed on the inoculated surface, the coated surface face down in the agar medium. After incubation at 37°C for 24 hours, the appearance of halo around the samples was analyzed by optical microscopy. A silicon (100) substrate and the a-C coating were also tested as controls. (B) Quantitative assay: 10 μ L of a cell suspension of *E. coli* K12 (ca. 10^4 cfu) were dropped onto the surface of the UV-sterilized samples. After 60 min of direct contact, the samples were placed into a 2-mL Eppendorf tube containing 1 mL of Luria-Bertani medium (LB broth lennox; Pronadisa 1231.00) and vortexed for 3 min at maximum speed. Afterwards, serial 10-in-10 dilutions were spread onto LB agar plates and cfu counting was carried out after incubation at 37 °C for 24 hours.

The concentration of silver ions delivered to the fluid in contact with the coated surfaces was estimated by inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectroscopy in Horiba Jobin Yvon equipment using the emission line of Ag at 328.07 nm. Coated samples were immersed in deionized water during 14 days. At predetermined time, the coating specimen was withdrawn and the resulting solution was measured by ICP-OES to determine the amount of released silver. After each measurement, the solution was renewed.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Tribological study of the a-C films

As a first approach, the tribological behaviour was studied using 100Cr6 steel balls in dry conditions to determine the self-lubricant properties in conditions similar to those typically employed for the characterization of DLC and carbon-based coatings. The obtained friction coefficients and the wear rates are plotted in Figure 1 as a function of the synthesis conditions (frequency and duty cycle). The measured friction coefficients of all samples are in the range of the reported values for carbon-based films measured in unlubricated sliding tests ($\mu \sim 0.15 - 0.25$) [43]. An increase is observed when the coatings are prepared with pulsed DC signals but no clear trend can be concluded from the influence of the pulse characteristics. For the wear resistance properties, the use of a high frequency (250 kHz) and a high duty cycle (90%) led to the lowest wear rate ($1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$). The observation of the films by SEM in cross-section and planar view (cf. Figure 2) demonstrated that the film morphology is columnar in all cases but showing smaller dimensions and separation between them for the sample exhibiting the lowest friction coefficient and wear rate values. As a result, these pulse DC conditions were selected for the preparation of the Ag-doped samples.

3.2. Structural and chemical characterization of the a-C:Ag films

A series of a-C:Ag films was deposited by using the optimized pulsed DC conditions with variable Ag content (from 1.2 to 23.4 at.%). The silver was incorporated by including different number of pellets (2, 3 or 4) in the sputtering racetrack. Figure 3 depicts SEM micrographs for the a-C:Ag coatings with a low (2.5 at.%) and high silver content (23.4 at.%). The cross-section pictures reveal the development of a columnar morphology on top of a titanium underlayer of approximately 300 nm. From the top view, the silver nanoparticles appear segregated at the column boundaries as bright spots. The size of the silver aggregates grows significantly in the sample with the highest Ag concentration (23.4 at.%). This phenomenon is consistent with the diffusion of Ag atoms along the film thickness and surface aggregation. Similar behaviour has been reported previously by other authors in Ag-DLC [44-47], Ag-TiN [48,49], and Ag-TiC [50] with larger silver segregation by increasing the noble metal content depending on the matrix. This process is explained due to the low miscibility of silver with carbon, the impossibility of forming carbide bonding, and the diminution of surface energy. The

outward mobility is favored by the presence of diffusion paths (pores, grain and column boundaries), compressive stress and thermal energy. The development of a top-surface continuous silver layer is sometimes observed if the transport rate of Ag atoms is sustained (aging) or enhanced (annealing) [51].

The particle size distribution along the film was studied from TEM and HAADF/STEM analysis. Figure 4a depicts a TEM cross-section view of the 2.5 at.% Ag sample showing the titanium interlayer and the dispersion of dark particles along the column boundaries and surface. A bimodal particle size distribution is denoted from the analysis of this sample by HAADF/STEM. Larger particles (20-70 nm) are found closer to the top surface as shown in Fig. 4b while a homogeneous distribution of bright small particles is observed at higher magnification (cf. Fig. 4d). In Fig. 4e, a HRTEM micrograph obtained from this latter area exhibits rounded particles with sizes varying from 2 to 5 nm. The nanoparticles display lattice fringes whose d-spacings of 2.0 and 2.3 Å can be assigned to the fcc-Ag phase. From a collection of pictures, the particle size distributions were estimated for each category with mean particle sizes of 10-20 (Fig. 4c) and 2 nm (Fig. 4f), for the large and small silver nanoparticles population, respectively. The increase of silver content in the a-C:Ag films brought a higher average particle size and more heterogeneous distribution (no micrographs shown). Similar results were obtained in Ag/a-C coatings with 20 at.% Ag prepared by dual magnetron sputtering [44]. The effects of silver segregation, coalescence and aggregation at the surface have also been studied by other authors recently [45-47]. The shape is also evolving from spherical towards polygonal and needle patterns due to the development of crystal facets. The presence of small particles is more desirable because they can enhance antibacterial properties [40,41] although a favorable contact with the solution at the Ag islands on surfaces may enhance the Ag dissolution.

Surface roughness plays an important effect on bacteria activity. Various groups have observed greater cell attachment on surfaces with high surface roughness [52]. Most common cells are between 0.5 and 5 µm. The measured average roughness values (R_a) of our coatings are found to be between 5 and 10 nm, with particular cases of higher values (15-25 nm) when formation of aggregates on surface takes place. Likewise, other authors have observed a similar trend in the surface roughness after incorporation of silver in the carbon film [32,33]. The film smoothness decreases the possibility of bacteria to establish contact and colonize surface. Nevertheless, it is possible that local

segregation of silver at certain points of the surface, as observed particularly in medium and high Ag contents, may increase the roughness significantly at certain specific points.

Another key factor in the cell adhesion properties is the surface energy. A low surface free energy, which is usually connected with higher contact angles, has been reported to be advantageous for good antibacterial properties [18,32]. However, other studies have shown that bacterial adhesion is promoted by the hydrophobic effect [53]. The wettability can be studied via contact angle measurements with polar and non-polar solvents. Angles above 90° reveal the presence of hydrophobic surfaces, while lower water contact angles imply a more hydrophilic character. In our case, water adsorption tests demonstrated the hydrophobic character of the a-C:Ag films with values above 110° independently of the Ag content. A superhydrophobic behaviour could be found ($\approx 180^\circ$) in the regions where silver has segregated forming metal islands. The hydrophobic nature was also confirmed for a-C film reference without silver giving a wetting angle of 85° . This result is similar to that found by previous groups [54-56] with values of 80° for the carbon reference and above 90° for the Ag-doped samples. Conversely, Alves et al. [57] reported a decrease of the contact angle in a different matrix (Ag-TiCN) although superhydrophobic values were also found in certain specific positions.

Raman spectroscopy was used to explore the variations of the carbon bonding structure after silver addition. The spectra (not shown) present the two prominent features, D and G bands centred at approximately 1350 and 1580 cm^{-1} , typical of amorphous carbon films. The D peak is attributed to the breathing modes of sp^2 atoms only in aromatic rings, while the G peak is attributed to the bond stretching of all pairs of sp^2 atoms in both aromatic rings and chains. These bands can be fitted by two Gaussian profiles and the intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) together with the G-peak position are commonly used to characterize the bonding structure [58]. Figure 5 shows the measured G peak position and calculated I_D/I_G ratio as a function of the Ag content. The obtained values are centred at approximately 1580 cm^{-1} and 1.2-1.4, respectively, showing no significant changes with the Ag incorporation. These values are consistent with a graphitic-like structure dominated by sp^2 hybridization, which does not modify significantly upon Ag enrichment. The low sp^3 character after inclusion of Ag has also been outlined in previous works [26,59,34]. Other authors have remarked an increasing sp^2/sp^3 trend

upon Ag enrichment but starting from a more sp^3 -bonded carbon matrix [60-62], which can be controlled by the deposition technique and experimental conditions.

3.3. Tribological and mechanical properties of the silver containing a-C films

3.3.1. Mechanical properties

Nanoindentation measurements were performed on five representative samples covering the range of Ag concentration studied in this work. As shown in Fig. 6, the hardness and elastic moduli exhibit a clear trend to decrease upon increasing the silver incorporation, particularly in the first part of curve. The hardness value is found to be 17 GPa in the a-C film and halves after introduction of ≈ 6 at.% of silver. From this point the values steady at approximately 6-7 GPa. Similar behavior was reported in Ag-doped TiN [49] or a-C(H):Ag [19,33,34,45,54,59]. The reduced elastic moduli follow a similar pattern with decreasing values from 180 to 92 GPa. The film softening can be explained by the increasing volume contribution of the Ag phase (soft) because Raman detected no significant variation of the sp^2 character of the carbon network. The low interaction between silver and carbon (not capable to form bonds), disrupting the carbon matrix network also contributes to decrease the hardness of the system [59]. Nevertheless, doping with silver reduce the internal stress of columnar films and results in high structural densification, adhesion to the substrate and ductility [51,60,62].

3.3.2. Tribological tests in unlubricated conditions

As a first approach, the tribological behavior of the a-C:Ag films was studied using the same testing conditions employed for the non-doped a-C series. The average friction coefficient and estimated wear rates values for all samples are summarized in Figure 7. Silver introduction induces a decrease in friction coefficient from 0.22 to 0.16, while the wear rate values increase slightly from 1.5×10^{-7} to $\approx 3 \times 10^{-7}$ mm^3/Nm . However, the tribological properties of the a-C:Ag films did not show a clear dependence on the silver content. Similar conclusion has been found in Ag-DLC [31], Ag-TiN [49] and Ag-TiCN coatings [63]. Some authors have reported a significant deterioration of the friction coefficient at high silver contents due to the segregation of silver and the consequent

degradation of the film beneath [31,34,64]. The slight decrease of wear resistance can be attributed to the diminution of the film hardness and strength.

Figure 8 shows the optical micrographs taken from the counterfaces at the end of the test for the a-C, a-C:Ag (2.5 at.%) and a-C:Ag (23.4 at.%). The observation of the wear scar can bring information about the processes occurring at the contact zone, which are influencing directly the tribological behavior. The film wear tracks appear rather clean and homogeneous, without signs of breaking failure or delamination. The debris particles are few and concentrated at the edges. The ball scars show however different aspect. In the case of a-C:Ag films the built-up of a layer is observed by accumulation of material transferred from the initial film. In the case of a-C, the third-body material does not agglomerate in the center and it is concentrated in an external ring, out of the contact region, surrounded by many loose debris particles. The formation of a tribolayer helps to accommodate the sliding motion, decreasing shear forces at the contact as happened in many solid lubricant systems (DLC, MoS₂, and MeC/a-C) [4,65,66]. The softer a-C:Ag films contribute to the transfer of material to the ball counterface in much extent and the presence of metallic silver can help to promote its adhesion to the steel ball [31]. In the absence of silver, the wear debris are more likely to be ejected from the contact region than stuck on the surface supporting that hypothesis.

The chemical nature of this tribolayer was studied by EDX analysis in a SEM. The secondary electron pictures shown in Figure 9 confirm the accumulation of material in the contact region, distributed preferentially in the center (a-C:Ag) or outside (a-C). The elemental chemical distribution maps of C, Ag, O and Fe revealed that the composition of these tribolayers are mainly carbon and silver from the initial film [64] while oxygen is associated to debris particles surrounding the contact region (a-C) or bare steel ball (a-C:Ag). The proportion of carbon is much less in the case of a-C confirming the limited thickness of this tribolayer and the enrichment in oxygen in the external ring.

The differences in the transfer film processes have an influence on the running-in period and average friction coefficient. Figure 10 plots the evolution of the friction coefficient with number of cycles for a-C and some selected Ag:a-C films with different amount of silver. The Ag-doped samples exhibit a diminution of the friction coefficient after a running-in period whose duration depends on the silver concentration. In agreement

with the microscopic study, increasing Ag contents favored the agglomeration of material in the ball counterface, diminishing the time needed to reach the steady-state.

3.3.3. Tribological tests in fetal bovinum serum (FBS)

With the aim of simulating the tribological conditions of materials in human bodies, the tribological tests were this time carried out in fetal bovinum serum at 37°C using alumina balls. Figure 7b summarizes the mean friction coefficient and wear resistance values for the set of a-C:Ag coatings. Again, the values of friction coefficient did not vary with the silver concentration giving an average of ≈ 0.15 . This result is very similar to that obtained with the previous tests (cf. Fig. 7a) except the a-C film whose friction coefficient is reduced from 0.22. The observation of the ball surfaces (not shown) did not reveal the formation of any tribolayer. Consequently, the response of this tribological system is more influenced by the characteristics of the biological fluid and the surface adsorption processes. Several authors have reported the benefits provided by the adsorption of proteins (albumin) on the tribological properties [57], which is favored by the hydrophobic character of the surface [67]. Nevertheless, we should also consider the graphitic-like character of the coating, which performs as a good lubricant in the presence of water. The film wear rates are also affected by the presence of FBS media. An overall reduction of k values is observed in liquid media with an average value of $9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ vs. 3×10^{-7} in dry conditions, even though an increment in the mean Hertzian contact pressure is calculated by using alumina balls (890 vs. 710 MPa with 100Cr6). This wear reduction can be attributed to the decrease of shear forces provided by the presence of the liquid serum and the formation of a protective layer of albumin molecules adsorbed on the surface in agreement with previous works [63,68]. These wear rate values were significantly better than previously reported in saline conditions $\approx 10^{-6}$ or $\approx 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ in Ag-TiCaPCON [69] and Ag-TiCN [63], respectively, although they were not tested exactly in the same conditions

Finally, the coatings were tested using UHMWPE balls as material antagonist in FBS at 10 N of applied load during 80000 cycles to mimic the conditions present in the implants. This polymer is commonly used in orthopedic applications as a component of joint parts due to its ability to accommodate shear and normal loads but it lacks of wear resistance. The Hertzian contact pressures are estimated to be of 27 MPa (average) and

40 MPa (maximum) under these conditions. Figure 7c plots the wear rate of the polymer ball (film wear is not measurable in this case) and the measured friction coefficient for a selection of samples. The specific UHMWPE wear rate was calculated using the volume of the spherical cap corresponding to the worn area measured on the UHMWPE surface. This wear rate value is believed to be overestimated since the observation of the ball scar (see inset in the plot) shows evidences of plastic deformation of the original microscopic crests of the UHMWPE rather than abrasion and material removal. It should be noted that no differences were found in the tribological properties depending on the orientation of the topographic features present in the commercial balls in respect to the sliding direction. Like in the previous cases, the friction coefficient did not show any clear dependence on the silver content. The average value is found in 0.20 versus 0.15 using alumina balls (cf. Fig. 7b). This small increment can be correlated with the roughness of the UHMWPE ball and higher adhesive chemical bonding between the ball and coatings, both of carbonaceous nature. No visible transfer is observed on the counterfaces although the adsorption of tribolayers cannot be disregarded. Concerning the ball wear rates, the values are comprised between 1 and 2×10^{-6} mm³/Nm. These data are comparable to those reported with Ag-ZrCN films against UHMWPE with silver contents ranging from 0 to 20 at.% [68]. No significant differences are demonstrated as a function of the silver concentration except for the highest value (21.3 at.%). This could be connected with a diminution of the adsorption of albumin as suggested previously [68].

In summary, the establishment of correlations for these tribological systems including materials with different mechanical, chemical and topographical features surrounded by a liquid biological media is complex as many factors are participating simultaneously. Nevertheless, the absence of a marked dependence of the Ag concentration on the tribological performance in the tested conditions is clear in most cases. The set of Ag-doped samples prepared by magnetron sputtering are characterized by smooth surfaces ($R_a < 0.03$ μm), hydrophobic character ($\theta > 110^\circ$), low hardness (6-8 GPa) and good tribological properties ($\mu \approx 0.15-0.20$ and $k \approx 10^{-7}$ mm³/Nm). The next step will consist in the evaluation of the antibacterial properties for proper selection of the optimum Ag concentration.

3.4. Antimicrobial properties

3.4.1. Halo tests

The antibacterial activities of a-C:Ag films against *E. coli* was firstly qualitatively assessed by determining the presence of inhibition zones by the disc diffusion assay (also known as halo or Kirby-Bauer tests). The antibacterial activities of a-C and Ag-mirror coatings were also tested for comparison purposes. In this test, the surfaces of the coatings are placed in direct contact with the biological media (agar-agar) containing the bacterial cells. The antibacterial activity is manifested by the appearance of a growth inhibition area in the vicinity of the sample. Figure 11 exhibits the optical micrographs of the obtained results. A marked fringe is observed in the a-C:Ag samples (Ag contents ranging from 2.7 to 22.0 at.%) but no contrast is observed in the references (pure a-C and Ag films) likewise in [70,71]. The size of the inhibition area appears to correlate with the concentration of silver but only if it is thoroughly dispersed in the film. A common behavior observed in the literature is the relationship between the amount of silver on the coating and the antibacterial ability [45,49,51,55,72]. However, less is reported about the size and distribution of the bactericide agent in the coating [27,41,47]. The null effectiveness of the Ag mirror is related to the high stability of Ag, which turns its ionization and solubility in water very low. Nevertheless, the formation of passive surfaces (e.g. insoluble silver halide or sulphide) can affect negatively the Ag release and hence activity [73]. This experiment demonstrates the advantages of dispersing Ag nanoparticles in a carbon matrix as good approach to favour a high concentration of Ag⁺ in cell surroundings, causing higher microbicidal effects, thanks to the high surface to volume ratio. The antibacterial action of silver is mainly addressed by the release of Ag⁺ ions, interaction with functional groups and membrane disruption by nanoparticle internalization [36,74,75]. To assess whether the antibacterial activity was bactericide or bacteriostatic, an aliquot of agar-agar was extracted from the inhibited area of 22.0 at.% of Ag and put in conditions for bacteria growth in a tube with 3 mL of Luria-Bertani liquid medium together with positive and negative controls. The absence of turbidity in the assay corresponding to the a-C:Ag sample proves the bactericide character of these films.

3.4.2. Lixiviation tests

As a complement to this study, the capacity of delivery of Ag^+ ions was evaluated by ICP from an aliquot taken from deionized water in contact with the coated samples at different times (from 1/2 to 14 days). Figure 12 plots the results obtained for a sample with 9.7 at.% of Ag in comparison with a pure Ag film prepared by magnetron sputtering. The selection of this intermediate silver content was based on the demonstrated bactericide behavior in the halo test, and to prevent cytotoxicity effects. Moreover, it has been recently reported that a Ag-DLC film containing 9.3 at.% Ag concentration yielded ~99.9% of antibacterial efficiency [61]. A significant difference in delivery rate (Fig. 12a) and total accumulated silver (Fig. 12b) is concluded from the comparison of the curves for both samples. The release of ions is much higher in the case of a-C:Ag film despite of its lower silver concentration in agreement with the experimental result obtained in the halo test. These results highlight the advantages of nanoparticles for delivery of the Ag^+ ions versus a continuous film due to increase of the specific surface area in contact with the solution [70,76]. The maximum delivery rate is attained at the third day with 0.24 mg/L. From this point the deliverance of silver starts to decrease gradually. In terms of total released Ag the amount reaches the 0.9 mg/L. This represents an average delivery of 0.115 mg/L*day during the first week. In the second phase the average delivery decreases one order of magnitude. This silver ion releasing is in agreement with previous reports revealing a sharp delivery at the initial stage and reaching a plateau corresponding to a steady-state [25,69,77,78]. Other works have reported the absence of antibacterial effects in some ceramic-Ag coatings such as Ag-MeCN or Ag-MeON (with Me = Zr, Ti, Ta) and the necessity of an additional process (visible light radiation or chemical oxidation) to activate the process [51]. The formation of a galvanic couple between the a-C and the silver nanoparticles has also been highlighted to positively influence the delivery of Ag^+ ions [70]. The evolution of the release of silver can be understood considering the changes in silver concentration and diffusion processes. At the beginning the surface is enriched in silver that promotes a rapid delivery. Then the delivery rate is limited by the transport of silver atoms to the surface and the inward diffusion of water through the column boundaries and pores. Other authors have reported lower values of released silver (in the ppb range) in graphitic [26] and different matrices: TiO_2 [25,75,76], ZrCN [68], TiCaPCON [69]. These differences can be attributed to the difficulties of the electrolyte to penetrate in the film, the dissolution of silver by strong affinity to the matrix. Other morphological features (nanoparticle size, density and surface aggregation) can definitively influence

the release of silver to the medium. The variability in the experimental conditions selected for the lixiviation test (nature and volume of the solution, specimen area, sampling) makes unfeasible the comparison and a definitive assessment of ion release capability.

To determine the silver release rate under a combined effect of friction and electrolyte immersion, the FBS solution in contact with the sample was analyzed at the end of the friction tests performed with UHMWPE (80000 cycles, 22 h). Figure 12c plots the dissolved Ag for a-C:Ag samples of 11.0, 14.8 and 22.0 at.% of Ag against the a-C as reference. It is demonstrated an increment of the silver liberated to the liquid in correlation with the initial concentration in the film. Comparing the results obtained for the sample of 11 at.% Ag with that obtained by natural lixiviation of a sample with comparable amount of silver (9.7 at.%), one can conclude that friction did not suppose a significant increment of the liberated silver as could be expected by gradual renewal of the surface, opening new pathways and exposing new fresh material to the solution. Other factors as the removal of silver aggregates at the top surface by the slider or the complex composition of the immersion medium (FBS), composed of inorganic salts and organic biomolecules, do not appear to affect significantly to the dissolution of silver from the coating.

3.4.3. Quantification of the antibacterial activity

To evaluate the influence of the Ag concentration in the antibacterial activity, a quantitative assay was carried out (see Experimental for details). Figure 13 depicts the results obtained with three different samples, a-C, a-C:Ag with 6.8 and 12.6 at.% Ag. A diminution of the number of colonies is observed with the increase of silver content. It should be noted that the concentration of the *E. coli* was diluted 10 times for the a-C samples to enable colony counting. Therefore, although the samples a-C and a-C:Ag (6.8 at.%) look like very similar the differences in colony number is of one order of magnitude. The plate corresponding to the highest amount of silver does not only show evidence of lower number of colonies but also a wider distribution in sizes. This higher heterogeneity in the dimensions of the colony assemblies, as compared to the a-C sample where they appear very similar in size and spherical shape, demonstrates a higher inhibition effect of the silver ions on the growth rate. It is well known that silver

cations are highly reactive species, which can bond easily negatively charged proteins or DNA damaging their structure [79]. The size of silver ion is also small enough to penetrate the bacterial cellular membranes and alter the enzymatic function. These factors influence negatively in the development of the bacteria and get a reduction of cell viability. Results obtained with other three samples with low (7.4 at.%), medium (12.6 at.%) and high (23.4 at.%) silver contents were summarized in Table 1.

The analysis of these results allows concluding that the silver doped samples yields a reduction of one or two orders of magnitude in the bacteria growth. The bactericide effect of the sample with intermediate concentration (12.6 at.%) resulted particularly interesting, in which no bacteria colony was found at the smallest dilution. As the contact angle measurements were similar for all the samples, the differences in antimicrobial effect can be directly attributed to the release of Ag^+ to the media. The ion delivery rate is influenced by the initial Ag concentration but also affected by other parameters as film microstructure, particle size and distribution in the film thickness, coalescence and surface aggregation, which can limit the access of electrolyte and particle dissolution. Particularly, the segregation of silver in the surface forming aggregates over the time is of extreme importance in order to estimate quantitatively the antibacterial effect and additional experiments with statistical analysis are advisable. Nevertheless, a positive response of silver doping for prevention of infection with *E. coli* was proved in all cases but considering that concentrations above ~7 at.% have demonstrated cytotoxic effects [80], the silver doping should be restricted below this threshold.

4. Conclusions

a-C films prepared by pulsed DC magnetron sputtering (250 kHz and duty cycle of 90%) were doped with increasing silver contents (from 1.2 to 23.4 at.%). The Ag nanoparticle size distribution broadens and the mean particle size grows as the silver concentration is increased. The nanoparticles are located either dispersed in the amorphous carbon matrix or in the column boundaries. A silver diffusion to the surface, particle coalescence and aggregation is manifested at increasing Ag contents. The chemical bonding of the a-C network and the tribological behavior were not modified significantly by the incorporation of silver. Nevertheless, a bactericide effect is proven

qualitatively and quantitatively by delivery of Ag ions to the liquid media. This release is controlled by the film morphology, Ag concentration and distribution, and surface aging. The fact that the tribological properties were not found to be dependent on the range of studied silver content is promising as an adequate compromise can be achieved between bactericide effects without damaging the tribological response. The ion release rate is maximum at 72 hours and diminishes significantly later. There is no clear effect of friction rubbing on the Ag ion release indicating that silver diffusion and top segregation are prevalent mechanisms for silver dissolution. This scenario is optimal for prevention of infections in short-term applications (e.g. prostheses implantation) when high delivery is needed after the surgery to avoid biofilm formation but restricts the detrimental effects on the osseointegration process.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Dependence of the tribological properties (friction coefficient and film wear rate) with the pulse characteristics (frequency and duty cycle). A carbon film prepared in non-pulsed mode (DC) is included for comparison.

Figure 2. SEM cross-section and top views of the a-C samples prepared with constant DC (a,b), and pulsed DC signals at 250 kHz of frequency and 90% (c,d) or 70% (e,f) of duty cycle.

Figure 3. Cross-section and planar view SEM micrographs of the a-C:Ag samples with 2.5 at.% (a,b) and 23.4 at.% of Ag (c,d).

Figure 4. TEM microscopic study of the a-C:Ag (2.5 at.% Ag) showing evidences of a bimodal particle size distribution. a) General cross-sectional view. b) HAADF/STEM micrograph illustrating the population of the largest particles and (c) corresponding particle size histogram. d) HAADF/STEM micrograph taken at higher magnification to prove the existence of small Ag particles embedded in the a-C matrix. e) HRTEM picture of Ag nanoparticles. (f) Particle size histogram of the smallest nanoparticle class.

Figure 5. G-peak position and I_D/I_G ratios obtained from Gaussian fitting of D and G bands of the Raman spectra of the a-C:Ag films.

Figure 6. Changes in the mechanical properties (hardness and reduced elastic modulus) as a function of the Ag content.

Figure 7. Friction coefficient and wear resistance values for the a-C:(Ag) films measured in unlubricated conditions vs. 100Cr6 (a), FBS vs. alumina ball (b), and FBS vs. UHMWPE ball (c). The wear rate value expressed in (c) corresponds to the wear of the polymeric ball.

Figure 8. Optical micrographs taken from the ball scars and wear tracks after the friction tests in dry conditions: a,b) a-C; c,d) a-C:Ag (2.5 at.%); e,f) a-C:Ag (23.4 at.%).

Figure 9. Secondary electron SEM pictures and associated elemental chemical distribution maps of tribolayers formed on the ball surface for a) a-C; b) a-C:Ag (2.5 at.%) and c) a-C:Ag 23.4 at.%.

Figure 10. Evolution of the friction coefficient with number of cycles for a-C and Ag:a-C films containing different Ag contents (2.5, 14.3 and 19.6 at.%) measured in unlubricated conditions vs. 100Cr6 balls.

Figure 11. Halo tests performed on a-C:Ag samples with variable Ag content. The reference samples (0 and 100 at.% Ag) correspond to a pure a-C and bulk Ag films.

Figure 12. a) Concentration of silver released from a-C:Ag (9.7 at.%) and pure Ag (100 at.%) films at different sequences of time. b) Accumulated silver amount in the liquid media for the same samples. c) Concentration of silver determined in FBS at the end of tribological tests performed with UHMWPE balls (22 h). The silver contents have been divided by the area exposed to the fluid to take into account the small variations of the sample size.

Figure 13. Bactericide effect of a-C:Ag films with two different concentrations (6.8 and 12.6 at.%). The *E. coli* solution used in Petri plate corresponding to the a-C is diluted 10 times with respect to the other ones.

Figure captions

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Figure 3. Cross-section and planar view SEM micrographs of the a-C:Ag samples with 2.5 at.% (a,b) and 23.4 at.% of Ag (c,d).

Figure 4. TEM microscopic study of the a-C:Ag (2.5 at.% Ag) showing evidences of a bimodal particle size distribution. a) General cross-sectional view. b) HAADF/STEM micrograph illustrating the population of the largest particles and (c) corresponding particle size histogram. d) HAADF/STEM micrograph taken at higher magnification to prove the existence of small Ag particles embedded in the a-C matrix. e) HRTEM picture of Ag nanoparticles. (f) Particle size histogram of the smallest nanoparticle class.

Figure 5. G-peak position and I_D/I_G ratios obtained from Gaussian fitting of D and G bands of the Raman spectra of the a-C:Ag films.

Figure 6. Changes in the mechanical properties (hardness and reduced elastic modulus) as a function of the Ag content.

Figure 7. Friction coefficient and wear resistance values for the a-C:(Ag) films measured in unlubricated conditions vs. 100Cr6 (a), FBS vs. alumina ball (b), and FBS vs. UHMWPE ball (c). The wear rate value expressed in (c) corresponds to the wear of the polymeric ball.

Figure 8. Optical micrographs taken from the ball scars and wear tracks after the friction tests in dry conditions: a,b) a-C; c,d) a-C:Ag (2.5 at.%); e,f) a-C:Ag (23.4 at.%).

Figure 9. Secondary electron SEM pictures and associated elemental chemical distribution maps of tribolayers formed on the ball surface for a) a-C; b) a-C:Ag (2.5 at.%) and c) a-C:Ag 23.4 at.%.

Figure 10. Evolution of the friction coefficient with number of cycles for a-C and Ag:a-C films containing different Ag contents (2.5, 14.3 and 19.6 at.%) measured in unlubricated conditions vs. 100Cr6 balls.

Figure 11. Halo tests performed on a-C:Ag samples with variable Ag content. The reference samples (0 and 100 at.% Ag) correspond to a pure a-C and bulk Ag films.

Figure 12. a) Concentration of silver released from a-C:Ag (9.7 at.%) and pure Ag (100 at.%) films at different sequences of time. b) Accumulated silver amount in the liquid media for the same samples. c) Concentration of silver determined in FBS at the end of tribological tests performed with UHMWPE balls (22 h). The silver contents have been divided by the area exposed to the fluid to take into account the small variations of the sample size.

Figure 13. Bactericide effect of a-C:Ag films with two different concentrations (6.8 and 12.6 at.%). The *E. coli* solution used in Petri plate corresponding to the a-C is diluted 10 times with respect to the other ones.

Table 1. Quantification of the antibacterial activity for three a-C:Ag samples with low (7.4 at.%), medium (12.6 at.%) and high (23.4 at.%) silver contents. The average number of bacteria was determined from the colony counting at three different dilutions.

Sample	10^{-1} dilution	10^{-2} dilution	10^{-3} dilution	bacteria (cfu/ml)
a-C (control)	uncountable	151	2	$8.6 \cdot 10^3$
a-C:Ag (7.4 % at.)	210	32	3	$2.8 \cdot 10^3$
a-C (control)	uncountable	179	16	$1.7 \cdot 10^4$
a-C:Ag (12.6 % at.)	43	6	0	$5.2 \cdot 10^2$
a-C (control)	uncountable	158	16	$1.6 \cdot 10^4$
a-C:Ag (23.4 % at.)	189	22	3	$2.4 \cdot 10^3$

0%

2.7%

5.9%

11.3%

22.0%

100%

a

a-C

6.8 at. % Ag

12.6 at. % Ag

1/10 Dilution

Highlights

- Ag-doped (1.2-23.4 at.%) carbon films are prepared by DC-pulsed magnetron sputtering.
- The tribological behavior is not compromised by the incorporation of silver.
- Small Ag particles are embedded in the a-C matrix ensuring antibacterial effect.
- Released Ag ions are determined in tribological tests mimicking the artificial joint.
- Silver doped samples yields a significant reduction of the *E. Coli* bacteria growth